

Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Education and Learning Outcome

Kamal Bhattacharyya

Professor, Faculty of Arts, Humanities and Social Science
Motherhood University, Roorkee, Haridwar (U.K.)

Received : 23/04/2023 1st BPR : 05/05/2023 2nd BPR : 16/05/2023 Accepted : 30/05/2023

Abstract

Artificial Intelligence is taking gradually but steadily over almost everything. The results and impact are now tremendous as people are excited. The consequences are considered on the basis of quick and readiness bereft its quality and justification. Science, Law, Medicine almost all subjects are being covered by AI. People are quickly learning to use them, as well as being indolent. Education as a whole is the biggest range of subjects that is now under the purview of AI. ChatGpt Open AI is now used rampantly by everybody from students, teachers to content creators. Modernization in education is always good for the posterity. It makes the learning outcome cognizable among the learners. To quote the Grail Knight from the movie Indiana Jones and the Last Crusade, the he said, "You must choose, but choose wisely as the true grain will bring you life, false grail will take from you." Artificial Intelligence may that grail and we must choose wisely for the benefit of the entire learner community and generations to come, as the true approach and method will bring life to education, wrong will take it from it.

Key words: Artificial Intelligence, Science, Law, Medicine, education, ChatGpt, Open AI, Grail.

Introduction:

Education as an umbrella term covers up all the subjects that human cognitive mind receives. No subject can go outside of the periphery of education. That is why education is very vibrant and polyhedral. In any country education gets always the priority for the sake of greater civilization. The countries that spend less on education, think less and remain less proactive in education remain in darkness. Technology progresses by dint of its own course. It is the human's cognitive mind that always flourishes towards betterment. Artificial Intelligence is one of the technologies that is now being used in almost every tangible and intangible things. From creating short story to rocket science man is taking the help of AI to reduce efforts and quicken the results.

AI will be a boon in medical education, where doctors have to go through series of experiments which are time consuming and expensive too. Detecting diseases, AI can play pivotal role in medical technology. Recently Google developed an AI that can predict heart disease and possibility of stroke by scanning the retina of our eyes. (Please refer to my article in the Times of India <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/readersblog/herbinger/artificial-intelligence-and-its-usage-in-microbiology-to-detect-diseases-50958/>)

AI is one of the branches of Computer Science. Algorithm and other automata are being used to construct AI. Websites and applications are now abundant for performing innumerable works for us. You go to the social platform, and you name it, AI will boggle our mind. Here are some examples of AI and their usage:

ChatGPT----Solves anything

Jasper AI----Writes anything

Synthesia----Creates Avatar
Do Not Pay----Consulting Legal affairs
Dall E-2-----Generates Art
Repurpose----Social Media
Jenni AI----Essays
Fireflies-----Note taking
Murf-----Text to speech
Timely-----Tracks your time
Quilbot-----Rewrite anything
Kuki-----AI Chatbot
Copy AI----Copywriting
Mailmentor-----Email writer
Andi AI----AI Assistant

What is AI:

AI is the machine that can infer its environment and take decision according which ratifies its success and carries forward it for longer period is called AI.

The objectives of Artificial Intelligence is not at all to replace human brain, but to juxtapose and help human intelligence to augment its power and ability to think, perform, decide. AI is based on different algorithm based on their performances and software used. Machine Learning, Big Data, Python are some of the languages that are used in making AI. Computer is brought under mimics cognitive so that it can think like human being. However human capacity of thinking is immense and varied and dynamic, machines cannot think in such ways that man can do. Andreas Kaplan and Michael Henline explained about AI: It is the machine that can take lesson from mistakes and act without pre-organized Meta data and evolutes.

When AI is used spontaneously, without being biased and effort, then the feeling of artificial intelligence does not stand as artificial. For example playing chess, driving car, defense simulation, and aero plane navigation using AI is not considered a big deal.

History of AI: AI started the storytelling in 1300 AD with Ramon Llull (1232-1316). Later on Gottfried Leibniz expanded the concept of the mathematical device or machine of which Wilhelm Schickard first engineered it in 1623 c) to operational functions rather than mathematical calculations. In later years, from 19th century AI came up in fictions per se Frankenstein by Mary Shelley or Karel kepec's R.U.R (Rasso's Universl Robots), television series Johnny Sokko and His Flying Robot (1967) won the heart of the children.

The Application of AI in Education:

History:

AI can be best fit in teaching history. In higher level, it can help to substitute carbon dating, recognizing old artifacts. It can create real image of old kings and queens by using augmented realities. The face of Kanishka can be artificially made by the help of AI.

Physics:

The king of subjects can be best explained by means of AI. The flow of current, the speed of light, the theory of relativity, quantum physics, static current all physical science knowledge can be explained by AI.

Geography:

The best usage of AI for geography or to be more specific Geology, would be to detect ores, waters etc. Future is much more waiting for prediction of earth quake, and AI can change the scenario and save lives and properties of the country.

Biology and Medical Science:

Life saving drugs, life saving operations can be conducted by AI with utter perfection. AI may perform non invasive and painless operation and treatment, like kidney stone, , Ankylosing Spondylitis etc.

Personalized Learning: The best application of AI is it is indefatigable; therefore AI can be used for personalized teaching and learning process. Tailor made syllabus, methods and application for individual students of slow learners and fast learners. AI can also be utilized in classroom situation as a subsidiary assistance, but might need good infrastructure, although, it would be the best idea to handle the AI as per the teachers cognizance. AI can help in building syllabus and rubrics for evaluation.

Adaptive Learning:

AI can create adaptive learning module which will define the perspectives of the learning outcome of individual students by the own face and cognition. This would strengthen the all over educational progress either in a class or in community. Adaptive learning is learners friendly by which MOOC course run on websites. However, MOOC courses are designed by the teachers and evaluation also done by them. If Adaptive learning is implemented it would do justice to the students and their evaluation.

Grading and Evaluation:

In Indian universities, especially in the private sectors, evaluation of answer scripts are nefarious. True and just evaluation of answer scripts would make a student perfect and errorless in his or her learning. Grading, CGPA, SGPA are all mathematical calculations that do not project the true spirit of the students learning outcome. I have seen better students with low CGPA. Teachers can be free and utilize their teaching and intense academic activities if AI can be used in evaluation. Adaptive question papers should be made for the students. In IITs I have seen, students are given books to find answers (Open Book Examination), and contrary, students were prepare to frame questions out of the context given in the answer booklet, instead of the question papers.

Implementation of Intelligent Subjects:

AI can also help to create subjects and topics for the future students. Subjects taught in school, colleges and Universities are sometimes outdated, which do not fetch relevance for the students. But in reality, no subjects in the world are inferior or bad. Artificial Intelligence can create subjects like Home Science, History, and Anthropology alive. The geometrical calculation, measurements, can be beautifully depicted and can be easily understood by the students. Why the value of pi is 3.14 can be easily explained by AI simulation

PIZZA

which we lacked in our days. How a Pizza can show you the same area of a rectangular shape by means of AI. The more you shall divide the pizza the more the triangle can be shaped into a triangle, therefore you can easily say $\pi r^2 = a^2 \times b^2$

(for details please refer to my article in the Times of India <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/-readersblog/herbinger/pizza-and-the-ancient-mathematical-illusion-52505/>)

If not manhandled AI can provide immense opportunities for better life and education. The framework of AI can be considered in the following criteria

1. Knowledge

2. Reasoning Capability
3. Problem Solving
4. Perception
5. Learning
6. Planning

During Covid AI helped in the 4th criteria in considering the future effect of the medicine and other variants of the virus. It would take longer time to assess the result of a new medication after experiments, but AI helped the whole human race by its analytical power, reasoning capability, problem solving.

There are two types of AI. Weak AI like Siri and Alexa and Strong AI like Tony Stark's JARVIS.

The good thing is AI not made of flesh and blood; therefore it can be controlled, managed upgrade and in case of emergency stopped. But we have to be careful about the malfunctioning of AI in high time, or if AI becomes harness free like Skynet (Refer to the movie Terminator). If AI can be used as demand and supply basis I think it would do better performance. Greed must be eliminated. In order to get the better and more benefits from AI in education, teachers from village to city must be trained well of AI. If teachers are not well aware of the AI tool handling, it would be very difficult to encourage the students. Gamification (is a method of teaching that NCERT promotes and for its analytical report please refer to my article in the Times of India ([https://timesofindia-indiatimes.com/readersblog-/herbinger/gamification-physical-digital-and-phygital-and-its-importance-in-education-for-equitable-and-life-long-learning-43542/](https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/readersblog-/herbinger/gamification-physical-digital-and-phygital-and-its-importance-in-education-for-equitable-and-life-long-learning-43542/)))

AI in preparing students for market ready:

Since AI is indefatigable therefore students would get lot of support from AI motivated teaching process. It would also be beneficial for the students as AI would cut the costs of Books and costly laboratory. AI will bring the cost of education down. Bill Gates told AI will be as good as human teacher soon.

In a conference in San Diego in California, Bill Gates uttered to a question from CNBC that very soon we will see AI playing the role of a teacher, teaching writing or mathematics.

Negative aspects of AI in education:

Artificial Intelligence is like dynamite, first invented by Alfred Noble, to break the chunks of mountains to make road, later lamented if he had not invented this since man started using dynamite as weapon. AI if not guided can have adverse effect on education. ChatGPT Open AI already started diminishing the LOTS (Lower Order Thinking Skills) and HOTS (Higher Order Thinking Skills). The application of AI should not be independently used by itself; rather it should be applied or utilized by an operator like a teacher can teach. Education is unfathomable subject. It should be kept pious for the sake of pure knowledge.

Bibliography:

1. Artificial Intelligence for All: Transforming Every Aspect of Life by Utpal Chakraborty
2. Rule of the Robots: How Artificial Intelligence will Transform Everything by Martin Ford, (Publisher Basic Book)
3. Learning For the Age of Artificial Intelligence: Eight Education Competences by AlanvM.Lessgold References:1. <https://curriculumredesign.org/wp-content/uploads/AIED-Book-Excerpt-CCR.pdf>
2. <https://www2.ed.gov/documents/ai-report/ai-report.pdf>
3. <https://rm.coe.int/artificial-intelligence-and-education-a-critical-view-through-the-lens/1680a886bd>

